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**MOBILITY ALTERNATIVES FOR THE ELDERLY:
AN ANALYSIS OF LOCAL INCENTIVE SCHEMES
IN GERMANY**

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INTRODUCTION

Enforcement, education, engineering and encouragement are used to influence the road safety behaviour (SCHADE, KÄMPFE, KECSKÉS AND SCHLAG 2003). In road safety work, incentive schemes (encouragement) are used to initiate behavioural changes but the incentive schemes do not focus on specific age groups and especially not on the growing target group of elderly road users (BOFINGER, FELD, SCHMIDT, SCHNABEL & WIELAND, 2018).

Experiments transfer the knowledge on incentive systems to the transport sector. ELIAS (2021) uses incentive schemes effectively to improve the safety of bus drivers whereas HULTKRANTZ & LINDBERG (2003) present evidence on car drivers. Furthermore, the general risk of car driving is known and the risk for elderly road users in particular (LANGFORD, METHORST & HAKAMIES-BLOMQUIST, 2006).

Less is known about the diversity of monetary incentives for road safety. WALUGA (2017) and TSELENTIS, YANNIS & VLAHOIANNI (2016) describe parts of the field in detail but omit others. Less is also known about the use of monetary incentives, especially to motivate elderly road users to change their mobility behaviour. Evidence is available for programmes to increase the use of public transport. However, no statements exist on elderly road users.

Too little is known about the design, influencing factors and effectiveness of programmes to motivate elderly road users to park their cars and use public transport. Therefore, the first research question is about which road safety incentives exist and how effective are they. The second is which instruments are effective to promote public transport use for elderly road users.

In this paper 115 incentive schemes are identified to promote the public transport use in exchange for a driving licence. It shows how smartphone-based incentives make roads safer and how alternatives to owning a car can be promoted for elderly road users.

The first section describes incentive systems for more road safety in general. The second section focuses on this incentive scheme for elderly road users, the details, the characteristics of relevant municipalities and the limitations. Finally, the paper discusses the instruments and draws a conclusion how road safety can be improved.

1. INCENTIVE SCHEMES IN ROAD SAFETY

1.1. INCENTIVES

Psychology differentiates between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation roots in the individual's needs. Extrinsic motivation roots in the individual's environment and the aim for wealth and status. Extrinsic motives can reinforce behaviour which occurs due to intrinsic motivation, but also alter it or be internalised (DECI & RYAN, 2000; KASSER & RYAN, 1996). The elements of extrinsic motivation include e.g. a higher status, reputation and economic success. Monetary incentives as used in the field of economics address the third example, economic success.

In economics, incentives affect prices and the relation between goods. Following the concept of opportunity costs in a two-dimensional setting, the costs of choosing one alternative are valued as utility loss from missing another alternative (BUCHANAN, 1999). Incentives change this relationship. GREEN (1968) discusses different fiscal incentives and illustrates the income- and substitution-effect. The income effect implies at given prices that an individual can afford more or less of a good. With incentives, the income effect is positive and indicates the higher consumption of a good. The substitution effect implies that the composition of a consumption bundle changes with the price of one good in it. Given an incentive, an individual can afford more of the funded good which affects the consumption of another good in the same bundle.

SCHADE, KÄMPFE, KECSKÉS AND SCHLAG (2003) show that monetary incentives reduce the benefit of risky road behaviour and increase the utility of safe behaviour. Concerning BECKER (2000), the authors adopt four functions of incentive schemes in the field of road safety. (1) Incentives activate the road users' existing motives for road safety and thus increase the commitment to a specific safety behaviour. (2) Incentives connect road users' behaviour with the goal of road safety by changing the type and the degree of the behaviour. (3) Incentives inform the road users explicitly about desired and undesired behaviour by rewarding it. (4) Changes in the traffic rules and requirements can be transported to the road users via incentives and may be adapted, if intended.

In general, the effect of incentives can be positive or negative in quality. In the background of road safety work, incentive instruments have a positive effect and are called encouragement. Incentive instruments with a negative effect include fines and other types of punishments, called enforcement. In this context, only instruments with a positive effect are relevant.

1.2. INCENTIVES TO PROMOTE SAFER DRIVING

H. M. BAUM, WELLS & LUND (1990) and FARMER (2019) demonstrate the effect of individual driving behaviour on road safety: A decrease in speed limit violations, fast driving, acceleration and braking is associated with less and less severe accidents.

The use of incentives to change driving behaviour during car use seems to be driven by at least two different developments in the car insurance sector. An early, rather theoretical application in the United States was the implementation of a surcharge at the gas station to price the accident risk per driven mile (TSELENTIS et al., 2016). After the liberalisation of the car insurance market in the European Union in 1994, insurance companies increasingly considered individual risk factors for accident risk assessment (EWERS, GROWITSCH, SCHWARZE, SCHWINTOWSKI & WEIN, 2004). Until today, car insurance companies maintain their prominent position in the development of instruments for accident risk assessment and offer telematic devices (telecommunication and informatics) for their customers. These devices allow for ex-ante risk assessment. Other users of telematic devices can be employers in the transport sector, parents of novice drivers, advertising companies and public authorities.

Several sectors use telematic devices today, especially insurance companies. The devices increase the effectiveness of conventional insurance schemes, while technical innovations support the distribution. Limitations apply to each field of application and the effectiveness differs. This section considers developments that have led to the current range of instruments.

Pay-how-you-drive – risk differentiation by car insurance companies

The literature shows that pay-how-you-drive car insurance schemes are the most important incentive to influence the behaviour of car drivers. Compared to others, it has fewer limitations, a large potential user group, a long history of development and fewer interests effect the design.

The pay-how-you-drive instrument uses data on the driving behaviour collected during vehicle operation. An algorithm computes a score from this data across all journeys within a specified period, e.g. an insurance year. Finally, insurance companies translate this score into penalty points, an insurance premium or a discount on a pre-defined premium (TSELENTIS et al., 2016). In the early development phase of pay-how-you-drive, on-board-devices were used for data collection (TRONCOSO, DANEZIS, KOSTA, BALASCH & PRENEEL, 2011). German insurance companies explain to use smartphones and probably receive more precise data if paring it with a GPS unit. The insured persons receive feedback on the incentive and their behaviour after each journey. The combination of the incentive e.g. a discount on the insurance premium and the feedback on the driving behaviour leads to lower accident risks.

In field experiments, the driving behaviour was measured in categories of speed limit violations, sudden acceleration and braking, sharp turning, mileage and driving at night time. The experiments are divided into a pre-treatment-, a treatment- and a post-treatment phase. In all three experiments of HULTKRANTZ & LINDBERG (2003), BOLDERDIJK, KNOCKAERT, STEG & VERHOEF (2011) and DIJKSTERHUIS et al. (2015), the reduction in speed-limit violations is significant, but other parameters are not. In HULTKRANTZ AND LINDBERG (2003), the reduction during the treatment is up to 50 % compared to 30 % in the post-treatment phase. In the post-treatment phase, results differ between a reduction relative to the pre-treatment phase and a full recovery. DIJKSTERHUIS et al. (2015) found that in-vehicle- feedback is stronger than delayed web-based feedback, whereas a control group showed no effect.

A reduction in risky driving behaviour supports road safety. BRIJS, WETS, KRIMPENFORT AND OFFERMANS (2006) write that speed variations above the average increase the accident risk. PAEFGEN et al. (2014) result in a higher accident risk on weekdays, in the evening- and at night. Drivers are safer in the morning hours (VERBELEN, ANTONIO & CLAESKENS, 2018) and experienced drivers are less at risk at night times than novice drivers (AYUSO, GUILLÉN & PÉREZ-MARÍN, 2014). VERBELEN et al. (2018) reveal that the accident frequency decreases in the trip-length, as the share of motorways rises. PAEFGEN, STAAKE & FLEISCH (2014) show that monthly mileage increases the accident risk, but the higher the experience, the more time passes until an accident (AYUSO et al., 2014).

Advantages to related instruments are that the premiums are not biased due to marketing reasons in its pure version and that the scope of different variables allows an individual risk assessment. Technical limitations decreased as smartphones became more important, but on the contrary privacy concerns remain to be an important reason against participation. Pay-how-you-drive instruments reduce accident-related behaviour in field experiments, the implementation is technically easy and individual risk assessment improves.

Pay-as-you-drive – risk differentiation by car insurance companies

Pay-as-you-drive is a precursor of pay-how-you-drive instruments. It assesses the accident risk by mileage and roots in the positive correlation with more accidents (TSELENTIS et al., 2016). Since the emergence of pay-how-you-drive instruments, it is incorporated into these.

The pay-as-you-drive instruments use data on the mileage collected during vehicle operation. An on-board-device is used for the data collection. The insurance premium is either determined on a continuous or a discrete basis. The insured persons receive feedback after the journey or, in the case of a field trial, also during the journey on a display (LITMAN, 2011).

The effectiveness of such instruments was investigated, based on mileage data, insurance data, elasticities and differing approaches. All studies resulted in a mileage decrease, but the

magnitude is not comparable. PARRY (2005) results in costs per mile of USD 0.12 in a 3.64 % decrease in fuel consumption due to lower mileage, which partially roots in the reduction of the number of cars. BORDOFF & NOEL (2008) results at costs per mile of USD 6.6 on average (range from USD 5 to 9.7) in an 8 % mileage reduction on average (range from 5.7 to 13.5%). Other effects were not investigated. In a field experiment, BUXBAUM (2006) investigated the effect of a premium drawn from between USD 0.05 and 0.25 per mile and deducted from a reward for participation in the experiment. Limitations apply to the selection of participants and the choice of vehicles, but the effect equals a 9.6 % reduction on weekdays and an 8 % reduction on weekends. The premiums differ according to the weekday and the time of the day.

Similar limitations apply as to pay-how-you-drive instruments. The data transmission was less advanced at the early stage and risk assessment less precise. The instrument stopped that low-mileage drivers subsidised high-mileage ones. With the technical evolution, it lost importance.

Merit-rating system – risk differentiation by car insurance companies

The merit rating system as main pillar of car insurers can be combined with pay-how-you-drive.

The merit-rating system allows the claims history of the insured persons to be considered. If they remain claim-free over a certain period, this is rewarded by a premium reduction or otherwise sanctioned by an increase (H. BAUM & KLING, 1998). Characteristics like age and region of residency are also considered when calculating the basic premiums (EWERS et al., 2004). Since the merit rating system is an ex-post risk assessment, HEINZMANN & SCHADE (2004) used data from the Central Card-Index for Traffic Offences for an early ex-ante risk assessment. The accident risk increases with the number of entries. The instrument was not implemented, because privacy concerns and data transmission issues are still unanswered.

Following HULTKRANTZ & LINDBERG (2003), limitations of the merit-rating system apply according to the premium reduction, penalties after accidents, options to insure against a penalty and the absence of an actual risk assessment. Insured persons after many years without accidents face only a small share of the premium reduction in the early years. The incentive shrinks. Simultaneously, the penalty after an accident is lower than in the early years and insured persons can avoid penalties for an additional premium. The ex-post risk assessment and these limitations lead to the subsidisation of risky drivers by good drivers. Thus, the idea of the merit-rating system was rated better than alternatives at that time but lost effectiveness in practice.

Variable remuneration systems

Professional drivers with high mileage are at risk and the application of telematic devices is similar to the insurance sector. In contrast to non-commercial car use, businesses compete and

weigh safety gains differently against costs and time savings. Variable remuneration schemes are of minor importance yet.

ELIAS (2021) investigated the effect of bonuses on the driving behaviour of male bus drivers. Parameters are speed limit violations, tailgating and frequent lane changes without signalling. In two specifications, a fixed sum of bonuses was either paid to the best driver or the best half of them and nothing in a first specification. Every evening, the participants got information about the bonus via text message.

The experiment resulted in a reduced occurrence of risky behaviours and showed a stronger effect with smaller bonuses for a larger group of drivers. The effect was still significant, short after the treatment phase. It is important that the risk composition of the treatment groups differs and that the effects in both groups are reported separately.

Limitations apply in that safer driving and incentive costs may conflict with income-maximising behaviour. The results of ELIAS (2021) support the use of bonuses in the context of road safety, but further research is necessary.

Vouchers

The promotion of road safety with vouchers is less common, but fields of application like parents of novice drivers and employers are likely.

Participants receive a voucher based on a score derived from various characteristics of their driving behaviour. HULTKRANTZ & LINDBERG (2003) used speed limit violations and the bonus decreased with the number of cases. MAZURECK & VAN HATTEM (2006) used speed limit violations and tailgating. The participants earned points, which they used for rewards. The best driver of the month received additional points. REAGAN, BLISS, VAN HOUTEN & HILTON (2013) used speed limit violations. The participants earned bonuses for the time driving below the speed limit and paid a fee for the time driving above the limit. Participants received feedback on their driving behaviour and the incentive while driving. MULLEN, MAXWELL & BÉDARD (2015) used speed limit violations and the number of accidents on a simulator. The participants used the earned points for gift cards from a shop. Participants received feedback on their driving behaviour while driving. Except for this experiment, all were field experiments.

The incentive effectively reduced the number of speed limit violations in all experiments. REAGAN et al. (2013) and MULLEN et al. (2015) found that incentives and the combination of incentives and feedback have a significantly stronger impact than feedback alone. While the latter study MAZURECK & VAN HATTEM (2006) results in a return to the original driving behaviour, HULTKRANTZ AND LINDBERG (2003) measured a longer-term effect of the incentive system. A comparison of the different quantities resulting from the various studies is

difficult. This is due to the different approaches, such as the use of feedback, the design of the incentive in terms of quality and degree of differentiation, the choice of reference groups/periods and the lengths of the individual trial periods.

The instrument allows an individual risk assessment. Technical limitations are low as most people have smartphones and the data quality is not as important as for car insurance, but privacy concerns are important. Vouchers reduce accident-related behaviour in field experiments, the implementation is technically easy and e.g. young drivers receive feedback. It is ambiguous whether companies or public agencies will set up and offer such an instrument.

Smartphone use

The US Federal Highway Administration and other studies investigated monetary incentives to reduce smartphone use while driving.

The participants in the different experiments used a smartphone app to track their smartphone use in terms of physical phone interaction. They received feedback on their smartphone use and an incentive. Depending on the study, the incentives were to participate in a lottery, to receive cash payments at the end of the experiment and to receive cash payments at different steps during the experiment. The Federal Highway Administration (2022) used the most advanced incentives. In one specification, participants received an incentive paid at the end of the experiment without feedback. A second group received the same incentive and a weekly comparison to the other participants. A third group received a weekly incentive depending on their relative position to the other participants, plus the weekly comparison to the other participants. In total, the incentive equalled the size of the first two groups. A fourth group tested a similar setting as the third group, except with a twice as high incentive. Additional groups formed a control group and a feedback-only group.

The Federal Highway Administration (2022) resulted in a significant reduction in smartphone use while car driving. The results for the feedback-only group and group 1 with an incentive after the end of the experiment and no weekly feedback were insignificant. The combination of weekly feedback and an incentive resulted in significant reductions for groups 2, 3 and 4. The results were strongest for group three with a 22.7 % decline in smartphone use. The results for group 4 equalled 17.4 % and 15.7 % for group two. HENK, MUNIRA & TISDALE (2021) also resulted in an effect of the app-based feedback in combination with an incentive for the user group up to 25 years old. In contrast to the Federal Highway Administration, top performers participated in a lottery. The decline in smartphone use was significant for participants from 15 to 17 years old and female drivers. Although these results are not as strong as in Federal Highway Administration (2022), they are similar to the results for group 2 with a similar setting.

The Federal Highway Administration (2022) shows the limitation that the incentive leads to a reduction in smartphone use while driving, but not to abandonment. Car drivers are less distracted but still distracted. Commercial apps already use incentives that are comparable to weekly incentives which reduced smartphone use. It remains unanswered if these reduce the number of accidents though, if the users may still be distracted in risky situations.

1.3. INCENTIVES TO CHANGE THE MODE OF TRANSPORT CHOICE

The second application of incentive theory in the field of mobility behaviour aims for a change from the car to alternative modes of transport. Literature demonstrates that driving in cities is associated with a higher number of accidents (AYUSO, GUILLÉN & PÉREZ-MARÍN, 2014) and (VERBELEN, ANTONIO & CLAESKENS, 2018). MARTIN (2002), WANG, QUDDUS & ISON (2013) and PARK & LORD (2007) result in an increase in accidents with light injuries with an increase in car traffic density, compared to severe and fatal accidents. Hence, a decrease in car traffic in urban areas reduces the number of accidents. The severity of accidents does not rise if the traffic density remains constant due to the accompanying reduction in road capacity.

Cities across Europe and around the world price the usage of urban roads to reduce congestion, finance infrastructure projects and reduce the number of accidents. Examples are London, Stockholm and Singapore as described by ERDMENGER, HOFFMANN, FREY, LAMBRECHT & WLODARSKI (2010). Other, but less relevant examples of instruments are the pricing of parking areas and motorways. Another area of application is the promotion of public transport services. The city of Cologne tested a buddy program. A similar approach is the new-citizen ticket, a free ticket for the first months with additional information.

The instruments change the behaviour of road users. Urban road pricing led to a decline in the number of road users, to less congestion and in some cases the experiments report a reduction in the number and the severity of accidents. Cities which promote free public transport trials to their new and senior citizens report a higher number of subscribers at the end of the free trial period. Some reports also focus on the reduction of car use among the participants.

Urban road pricing

Singapore, London, Stockholm, Rome, Melbourne, Durham, Santiago de Chile and New York are among the cities which implemented road pricing schemes (MIETSCH, 2007). The most important success factors are: If the congestion charging zone is too small, traffic locates around it and entering traffic is too small. If the zone is too large, journeys inside the zone are not charged (ERDMENGER et al., 2010). In a city with only one city centre, the people commute into the zone, but with several sub-centres, the commuting traffic relocates around the congestion charging zone (ERDMENGER et al., 2010). The same accounts for regions with a

large density of cities (SIEG, 2020). The number of arterials determines the administrative costs PHANG & TOH (2004) since the costs depend on the equipment to control the entering traffic.

The examples from Milan (CROCI, 2016), London (Transport for London, 2005) and Stockholm (BESER HUGOSSON & ELIASSON, 2006) report a decline in accidents of 21.7 % for Milan, 9 % for London and 5-10 % for Stockholm after the introduction of the congestion charging zone. Transport for London (2008) reported a decline of 3 % in severe accidents and 10 % in light accidents 1 year after the introduction of the congestion charging zone. Luckily, the number of fatalities was too low for significant results. For cities with varying fees, the demand elasticity of a price increase implies a certain percentage decrease in demand at a 1 % price increase. Table 1 shows demand elasticity between 0 and -1 and also significant traffic reductions after the introduction of a congestion charging zone for European cities. The 85 % reduction for Durham is a ten-year comparison and the interpretation is difficult.

The examples from European cities report that urban road pricing effectively reduces the traffic, the number and the severity of accidents. Limitations apply concerning the degree of centralisation, the size of the congestion charging zone, the costs and the relevance. Thus, urban road pricing is an important instrument for more road safety. It requires cooperation among municipalities and alternatives like the pricing of parking areas can be better if requirements are not fulfilled. RUDOLPH (2015) investigated the effectiveness of this alternative.

City	Traffic	Demand elasticities
London	-21 % CCZ; -14 % WEZ ⁽ⁱ⁾	-0,42 CCZ; -0,47 WEZ ⁽ⁱⁱ⁾
Stockholm	-20 % ⁽ⁱⁱⁱ⁾	-0,85 ⁽ⁱⁱⁱ⁾
Milan	-38 % ^(iv)	-0,46 bis -0,66 ^(v)
Rome	-10 % ^(vi)	
Durham	- 85 % ^(vii)	
Bergen	-6 bis -7 % ^(viii)	
Oslo	0 bis -10 % ^(viii)	
(i) Transport for London (2005)		(v) CROCI (2016)
(ii) Transport for London (2008)		(vi) MIETSCH (2007)
(iii) BÖRJESSON, ELIASSON, HUGOSSON & BRUNDELL-FREIJ (2012)		(vii) HARLAND (2003)
(iv) NUCCIO (2019)		(viii) HALBRITTER, FLEISCHER, KUPSCH, KLOAS & VOIGT (2005)
CCZ = Congestion Charging zone		WEZ = Western Extension Zone

Table 1: Traffic reductions and demand elasticities

Public transport for new citizens

New citizens in a city are confronted with an unfamiliar environment, other places become important, routing takes place and new transport habits develop.

The municipality administrations contact new citizens by mail, share information about the public transport network as well as important places and make recommendations. The letter also contains a form to apply for the new citizen ticket. The ticket is valid for a limited period. Recipients are offered a public transport subscription at the end of the free trial period. Success factors are the early welcome letter with additional information (FARROKHIKHIAMI, 2010; LOOSE, 2004), individual profiles for each target group (WAPPELHORST, 2009) and the alignment with a broader mobility concept (Stadt Tübingen, 2019).

The German cities Aachen (FARROKHIKHIAMI, 2010), Munich (WAPPELHORST, 2009), Offenburg (LOOSE, 2004) and Tübingen (Stadt Tübingen, 2019) tested tickets for new citizens over a period between 4 days and 8 weeks. About 30 % of the recipients in Aachen and 17 % in Offenburg cashed their vouchers. In Aachen, the share of recipients who have not used public transport before decreased by up to 4 % during the treatment phase. In the control group, the number of non-users even increased. Munich observed an increase in public transport use of 7.6 % compared with the control group and Offenburg simply concludes that the use increased due to the offer. The use of public transport in Tübingen did not increase, but the free trial period was with 4 days the shortest among the 4 cities. Munich reported a simultaneous decrease in the use of cars and bicycles.

Limitations apply to the size of the target group and the demand. In Tübingen, 14 % of the subscribers for the free trial period have not used the ticket at all. Besides the reduction in the car-use, Munich reports unintended demand effects on the use of bicycles. The comparison with a control group shows that the instrument can be effective in increasing the use of public transport and reducing car traffic. This depends on the communication with the target group, and probably on the incentive duration. Tübingen further suggests offering incentives for young mothers to use cargo bikes and car-sharing offers if mobility habits change after birth.

Buddy program and reduced tickets for elderly road users

The city of Cologne invited elderly public transport subscribers to take a free subscription for three months and give it to a friend of the same age. The subscribers act as buddies, receive coaching and assist their friends to use public transport during the free trial period.

S. SCHUBERT (2009) reports that 56 % of the new public transport users drove a car. During the experiment, the demand for all modes of transport decreased, except public transport. It increased. After the experiment, 30 % of the new public transport users subscribed for a senior ticket. These senior tickets are subscriptions and cost half of the regular fare and spouses save another 50 % on the reduced fare in many cities. Sometimes, the validity period starts after the commuter traffic at 8 or 9 am or the senior tickets qualify for first-class access in regional trains. During the experiment, the buddy program caused a shift from the other modes of transport towards public transport. The city of Cologne decided not to extend the project.

Driving licence exchange

German municipalities introduced incentive schemes, mostly targeting elderly road users. In order to lower the barriers to using mobility alternatives, increase road safety and promote social activities, public transport operators offer free tickets in permanent exchange for a driving licence. No literature exists, but the number of municipalities with such instruments increases.

Interested people visit the road traffic licencing department, declare their driving licence relinquishment and that they will no longer drive a car. They receive a receipt from the road traffic licencing department and present it at a service centre of the public transport operator to receive the incentive. After the driving licence relinquishment, people can apply for a new driving licence, but the burden to prove their driving ability reverses. The authorities are no longer in charge.

A preliminary data collection started with an internet search for exchange offers and revealed 115 offers to exchange the driving licence for a public transport ticket. After dropping previous versions of an offer for the same municipality, the data set consists of 108 offers.

To complete the list of municipalities, collect missing data and gain additional insights, a survey has been launched among German municipalities. It was designed as an online survey among 432 public transport operators all over Germany. The survey is divided into 6 parts. The data collection relates to the status of the scheme, the use of subsidies, the scheme design, the demand for the offer, information channels and the transport network.

The analysis investigates impacts on the effectiveness of driving licence exchange offers. The second question is which characteristics municipalities have if they decided to make these offers. The new nationwide “Deutschlandticket” starts in May. It has the potential to take the demand to a new level. According to the users, the number of users and their share in the population of the hometowns are relevant. A phenomenon is free-riding, but it is ambiguous whether this is a problem. Further interviews will provide more insights.

The aim is to provide information and develop a guideline for municipalities to improve existing offers. The instrument is useful to raise awareness for the topic among elderly road users. Like all incentives, it changes the demand curve via a substitution- and an income effect. Public transport becomes more attractive - the more, the stronger the incentive.

What happened so far? I prepared a list of municipalities with such an offer, collected municipality-specific data at the district-level, drafted, pre-tested and launched the survey, tested my model on randomly generated data and held expert interviews. After the two-stage data collection, the analysis will follow. Additional expert interviews will strengthen the results on free-riding and the expected effect of the nationwide “Deutschlandticket”. Results are expected in the early fall of this year.

2.DISCUSSION

The Literature describes pure incentives and the combination with feedback or a social component. Pure incentives reduce dangerous behaviour. The combination of feedback and incentives exceeds the pure incentive effect. Feedback informs directly about the driving behaviour or indirectly via the size of the incentive. In Federal Highway Administration (2022) feedback on the size of the incentive made the incentive effective. REAGAN et al. (2013) assume that feedback is the difference to studies without incentive effect. MAZURECK & VAN HATTEM (2006) and MULLEN et al. (2015) highlight that in-vehicle feedback is important and even exceeds the effect of feedback on the incentive only. Disadvantages of feedback are privacy concerns and barriers for non-technophile people, many elderly. Otherwise, these incentives precisely change behaviour and opting in or out is easy at low administrative costs. Participants treated the incentive condition as a game (REAGAN et al., 2013). In the long term, the effect diminishes and can disappear when the treatment ends.

Feedback is used when changing the driving behaviour and the social component for the mode of transport. Communication for the new citizen ticket highlights public transport to engage socially in a new environment. Adds for discounted senior tickets argue to take relatives and friends or focus on an additional discount for spouses. The buddy program focuses on shared experiences and a tutoring system. Disadvantages of incentives with a social component are that the effect is not precise, affects all modes of transport and causes administrative costs. There are no technical barriers, communication is personal but opting in is time-consuming. Minimum duration and notice periods make opting out expensive, regaining the driving licence may be impossible and the obstacle to opting in increases beforehand.

Incentives with feedback are not suitable for elderlies with less experience in modern telecommunications technology. Insurance- and voucher-based instrument are similarly effective. Pay-how-you-drive improves by reducing competing interests, introducing in-vehicle feedback and fostering the distribution. Incentives against smartphone use do not stop distraction and variable remuneration may not be in line with the market. Most effective to stimulate public transport use is urban road pricing, but not suitable for many cities. Transferring the idea of the new-citizen ticket to people reaching the pension age will also be effective at low barriers. The buddy program was not extended and the effect of the driving licence exchange is ambiguous yet.

3.CONCLUSION

Incentive schemes increase road safety by changing driving behaviour and the mode of transport. The first question relates to effectiveness. Among the instruments which change driving behaviour, pay-how-you-drive and the use of vouchers are very effective. Insurance companies increasingly address the target group, but voucher-based solutions need promotion. These concepts do not increase public transport use. Urban road pricing does. More research is necessary to make roads safer for elderly road users. Concerning the second question, urban road pricing is effective and includes elderly road users. More specifically, tickets for elderly road users reaching pension age have a high potential to promote public transport usage. At this time transport habits and the purpose of the car change. Offers to exchange the driving licence also stimulate public transport usage. I currently investigate this instrument and how the effect works. It needs more offers to transfer the knowledge about the accident statistics into improvements for the road safety of elderly road users, e.g. for bicycles, pedicels and pedestrians.

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